

APPENDIX A

Nitrogen isotopes in tooth enamel record diet and trophic level enrichment: results from a controlled feeding experiment

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

SECTION A1: Pre-treatment evaluation for modern and fossil tooth enamel

TABLE A1: N content and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values for all in-house standards and enamel samples for each pre-treatment type.

TABLE A2: Summary statistics for $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{soft tissue}}$ values for each individual from the feeding experiment

TABLE A3: $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values for all measured tooth enamel samples from the feeding experiment

TABLE A4: $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values for all measured samples for the cleaning test

FIG. A1: N content and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values for all in-house standards and enamel samples for each pre-treatment type.

FIG. A2: Image of rodent incisor sampled from the controlled feeding study

FIG. A3: $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{immature enamel}}$ versus $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{soft tissue}}$ values

Pre-treatment evaluation for modern and fossil tooth enamel

While the overall objective of the controlled feeding study was to determine whether $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values record a dietary signal, we also sought to determine the optimal method for removing exogenous organic matter from tooth enamel prior to $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ analysis, with the goal of applying the denitrification-oxidation method to fossil enamel in future studies. Previous $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ studies of marine microfossils (e.g., diatoms, foraminifera, corals, fish otoliths) using this method have demonstrated the necessity of a chemical cleaning step prior to measurement to remove potentially confounding exogenous nitrogen from the sample (e.g., Ren et al., 2009; Bright and Kaufman, 2011; Wang et al., 2014; Lueders-Dumont et al., 2018). Given that diagenetic processes occurring during fossilization could potentially result in the deposition of exogenous nitrogen in tooth enamel (e.g., Kohn and Cerling, 2002; Koch, 2007), we adapted and tested two different pre-treatment methods, a bleach- and a reductive oxidative cleaning, routinely used to clean marine microfossils. We evaluated their applicability to both modern and fossil tooth enamel, by measuring $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values in a modern elephant tooth and four Plio-Pleistocene-aged

faunal teeth from the hominin-bearing Chiwondo Beds, Malawi, in the East African Rift System (Schrenk et al., 1995; Kullmer, 2008), listed in Table A1.

Three different sample types (coral, modern tooth enamel, and fossil tooth enamel; Table A1), were subjected to either an oxidative cleaning with sodium hypochlorite (i.e., ‘bleach-cleaned’), or a stepwise reductive-oxidative cleaning using buffered sodium dithionite and potassium persulfate solutions (i.e., ‘redox-cleaned’) prior to $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ analysis. These two methods have successfully been used for cleaning both aragonitic fossil material such as corals and otoliths or calcitic material such as foraminifera (Ren et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2014; Lueders-Dumont et al., 2018). To quantify the removal of exogenous nitrogen and related changes in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values associated with cleaning, a set of untreated samples was also run in parallel with the treated samples.

The measured corals include the two in-house aragonitic coral standards, PO-1 and LO-1. Because matrix type can impact the behavior of a sample during pre-treatment and oxidation, we also tested two in-house, matrix-matched tooth enamel standards (AG-Lox (modern), Noto-1 (fossil)) to evaluate the effect of these cleaning protocols on tooth enamel specifically. Additionally, three Plio-Pleistocene-aged fossil teeth from the hominin-bearing Chiwondo Beds in Malawi (T6, T7, T15, all from the same deposits which yielded Noto-1) were included to evaluate whether different fossil samples from the same deposit respond differently to the cleaning test. These fossil samples include one bovid (*Megalotragus* sp.; T7), and two equid teeth (*Eurygnathohippus* sp.; T6 and T15) for which ample powder was available for testing. The three additional fossil samples were subject to each pre-treatment type in duplicate.

Bleach-cleaned samples were soaked in 3 ml sodium hypochlorite (10–15 % available chlorine, Sigma-Aldrich), in muffled glass vials which were placed horizontally on a shaker table rotating at 110 rpm for 24 h. Samples were then centrifuged, bleach was removed by aspiration using a vacuum system, and samples were subsequently rinsed three times with Milli-Q water to ensure the removal of exogenous

nitrogen that was oxidized to nitrate or otherwise solubilized in the treatment. Samples were then dried at 60 °C in a dedicated drying oven.

Reductive-oxidative-cleaned (“redox”) samples were treated as described in detail in Section 2.2.4 of the main text, and samples which received no pre-treatment were directly oxidized and analyzed as described in Section 2.2.5.

In most of the samples analyzed for the cleaning test, the two cleaning methods (bleach and redox) resulted in similar N contents and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values (Table 4 and Figure 2). However, in one sample (T6, a fossil equid), the oxidative bleach-cleaning alone was insufficient to remove all exogenous nitrogen, resulting in significantly higher nitrogen content and lower $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values (see Figure A1 and Table A1) compared to the redox-cleaned samples and the other fossil samples from the same location. Redox-cleaning of this sample resulted in a significant decrease in N content and an increase in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values consistent with the removal of exogenous N. In addition, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values obtained with the redox-cleaning method (8.5 ± 1.1 ‰) were comparable with those obtained for the other fossil equid tooth (T15, 6.8 ± 0.2 ‰). These results suggest that exogenous N may be incorporated by the precipitation of metal oxides during the fossilization process, given that the reductive cleaning (i.e., removal of the metal oxides) appears to successfully remove this additional nitrogen. Consequently, we decided to use the redox-cleaning method described in Section 2.2.4 for all modern and fossil enamel samples, to ensure the removal of any exogenous organic matter.

Table A1: N content and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values for all in-house standards and enamel samples for each pre-treatment type.

MPIC ID	Material	Age	Taxon	N content (nmol/mg)			$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ (‰ vs Air)		
				No Cleaning	Bleach Cleaning	Redox Cleaning	No Cleaning	Bleach Cleaning	Redox Cleaning
PO-1	Coral	Modern	<i>Porites</i> sp.	3.8 ± 0.1 (3)	2.4 ± 0.3 (3)	2.5 ± 0.2 (21)	5.9 ± 0.0 (3)	5.5 ± 0.1 (3)	6.2 ± 0.3 (21)
LO-1	Coral	Modern	<i>Lophelia pertusa</i>	14.0 ± 0.0 (3)	1.6 ± 0.0 (3)	2.6 ± 0.1 (20)	9.7 ± 0.0 (3)	10.1 ± 0.0 (3)	10.1 ± 0.4 (20)
AG-Lox	Enamel	Modern	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>	44.2 ± 34.9 (3)	16.4 ± 4.2 (3)	12.1 ± 0.8 (21)	4.2 ± 0.2 (3)	4.0 ± 0.2 (3)	4.2 ± 0.5 (21)
Noto-1 (HRCP-762c)	Enamel	2.3–2.5 Ma	<i>Notochoerus scotti</i>	32.6 ± 31.2 (2)	6.1 ± 0.7 (2)	6.5 ± 0.6 (21)	10.6 ± 0.0 (2)	12.5 ± 0.4 (2)	13.6 ± 0.5 (21)
T6 (HRCP-847)	Enamel	2.3–2.5 Ma	<i>Eurygnathohippus</i> sp.	45.3 ± 21.3 (2)	34.6 ± 6.9 (2)	5.5 ± 1.0 (2)	2.9 ± 0.5 (2)	2.0 ± 0.1 (2)	8.5 ± 1.1 (2)
T7 (HRCP-361)	Enamel	1.7–0.6 Ma	<i>Megalotragus</i> sp.	8.8 ± 2.3 (2)	5.0 ± 0.6 (2)	4.9 ± 0.0 (2)	10.0 ± 0.7 (2)	14.5 ± 0.7 (2)	15.1 ± 0.3 (2)
T15 (HRCP-545a)	Enamel	>4 Ma	<i>Eurygnathohippus</i> sp.	10.5 ± 0.0 (2)	3.3 ± 0.1 (2)	4.1 ± 0.3 (2)	6.9 ± 0.2 (2)	6.4 ± 0.4 (2)	6.8 ± 0.2 (2)

Mean ± 1 standard deviation with n in parentheses

Figure A1: N content (A) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (B) for each enamel sample and pre-treatment type. Fossil enamel samples are indicated in the gray shaded region. N content in untreated and some bleach-cleaned samples was higher than in redox-cleaned samples. $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were lower in untreated samples than in cleaned samples for some specimens. Note, for fossil T6, N content was higher and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{enamel}}$ values were lower in untreated and bleach-cleaned samples. Redox cleaning of this sample resulted in decreased N content and increased $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values, consistent with the removal of exogenous nitrogen.

Figure A2: Image of a rat incisor from the controlled feeding study. The dashed line indicates where the tooth was cut in half during sampling to separate the highly mineralized, mature enamel of the tip half of the tooth from the poorly mineralized enamel of the root half of the tooth. The age (i.e., relative formation time) of the enamel is indicated by the arrow at the bottom of the figure. Mineralization decreases progressively towards the newly formed, open root

Figure A3: Soft tissue $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ vs. $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{immature enamel}}$ values for rats (triangles) and guinea pigs (circles) for plant- (green), insect- (yellow), and meat- (red) based diets. Error bars represent 1σ of replicates measured. As in mature enamel, soft tissue $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values are positively correlated with immature enamel $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values. Immature enamel follows the same pattern of trophic enrichment in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values observed in mature enamel (i.e., plant < insect < meat), but with lower average $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values. Unlike in mature enamel, rats and guinea pigs that received the insect-based diet do not differ in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values.